

A Good Design = A Good Mate

Ayça Çakmaklı

*Pratt Institute
New York, USA, cakmakli@gmail.com*

Abstract:

Industrial design has, in recent history, undergone a shift from form and function based design to “user-centered” and emotional design. As we’ve come to understand the value of emotionally connecting with consumers, the responsibilities of the contemporary industrial designer have grown. To be truly effective in this emotion-driven new space, designers must broaden their knowledge base to include fields like psychology, sociology, and anthropology. Design is about understanding people.

Using everything in their arsenal, designers try to create products that not only meet but exceed customers’ expectations; products that are so smart they anticipate their needs; products that adapt to changing situations; products that never fail when needed most; products that make people feel good about themselves; and even products that get more beautiful with age. As if designing an ideal mate, we want people to fall in love with what we create.

Social psychologists have for years studied and researched what it is that defines an ideal mate. In this paper, I argue that good design is a good mate, and I illustrate the direct links between the top traits of an ideal mate, as determined by social psychologists, and the traits most desired in good design.

But insight is only my first step. To facilitate the application of these insights, I have developed a series of helpful design strategies that link to each desired trait. Created as a deck of inspiration cards, designers can call upon these strategies when they wish to imbue their work with any of these emotionally potent traits.

Keywords: Design strategies, social psychology, traits of a good mate, traits of a good design, evolution and design, inspiration cards, design toolkit.

1. Introduction

Imagine you can design your own mate. What type of characteristics would you give him or her? Now imagine you can design your own product. What type of characteristics would you give that product? Are there similar attributes you would give to both such as beauty, trustworthiness and excitement? Between your two lists, there will be several overlaps. This is because we are constantly analyzing both people and products based on the same set of personal core values.

In order to safely and successfully navigate the complicated social ecosystem we live in today, people can be tough critics. Consciously or not, people analyze others according to the character traits they value most. Trust, ambition, empathy; we judge people based on how well they meet our needs both functionally and emotionally. People also analyze products in this way. In an attempt to surround ourselves with products that enrich our lives and make us feel good about ourselves, we analyze each object in terms of what it offers and how it resonates with our own values.

2. Incorporating Human Traits Into Design

2.1 Anthropomorphizing Products

Individuals talk about products the way they talk about people. In my research, I came across several individuals who referred to certain products as their best friend. For example, one research participant referred to her GPS as her most reliable friend. “I never worry when I’m out with her. I just tell her where we are going and she takes care of the rest. I can just sit back and enjoy the ride.” Many designers understand the power of personification in design. Car designers have been manipulating the face-like front end of cars for generations. Ceramicist Eva Zeisel awakens a dialogue between mother and child with a simple belly button-like indentation in a pair of vessels. The Roomba, a robotic vacuum cleaner, is a great example of behavioral personification. The Roomba gives feedback via specific sounds and movements alerting its owner of its current status or mood. Thusly, the user of the Roomba treats it as a pet. They talk to it, they brag about it to their friends, and they show affection for it.

We attempt to evoke a lasting emotional connection by giving products human-like features, but the decisions for which human attributes to personify have been largely based on designer intuition. We have not yet thought to start by defining what it is that humans really desire- what the ideal traits of humans are. This is where my work begins. I am interested in calling upon various fields of expertise to identify the top traits we look for in our long-term mates. These traits in our ideal mates have been selected for over generations and therefore create a deep emotional connection. And if our goal as designers is to provide work that conjures these emotional connections, then imbuing our designs with these top traits can help.

2.2 Brief Overview of Trait Selection

Trait selection has been studied for several decades mainly in the fields of psychology and sociology. Norman Anderson was the first social psychologist to identify what traits define the most “likable” people. In 1968 he obtained normative likableness ratings of 555 personality trait adjectives, from the English dictionary and, through extensive studies, identified the top ten traits that were the most likable in people. These are: *Sincere*,

honest, understanding, loyal, truthful, trustworthy, intelligent, dependable, open-minded, and thoughtful. In 1989 psychologist David M. Buss expanded upon Anderson's work by studying the traits people value most in long-term mates. He revealed that men and women agree that *kindness, understanding and intelligence* are the traits most valued in a long-term mate. Building upon Buss' findings, psychologist Garth Fletcher revealed that *Warmth, vitality, attractiveness* and social *status* were the most valued traits in mate selection [1].

2.3 Methodology of Defining the Ideal Traits

To determine the traits we value most in our long-term mates, I collected and read through all of the "ideal trait selection" and related studies written by social psychologists. I tallied the most common ideal trait adjectives used and organized my research results into synonym categories. With this information, I discovered the top 7 traits we desire most in our long-term mates.

Noticing abundant similarities between the traits I had discovered and product discussions from my work in the design field, I decided to share my seven traits with the design world, looking for insight. I organized interviews, discussion guides, shop-alongs and home visits to gather a broader opinion of the adjectives I had arrived at and their connection to product design. Again, I recorded commonly used adjectives when discussing products and then organized them into synonym groups. This reaffirmed my hypothesis that these 7 traits most important in mate selection are just as important in product selection.

3. The Top 7 Traits

The following section illustrates the 7-trait framework that I have designed as a result of my research findings. Each trait is defined by a major heading derived from my research. This heading is accompanied by a series of similar words derived from my research into product design. Each trait is analyzed, first from an evolutionary standpoint of mate selection, then from a design standpoint of product selection.

3.1 Attractiveness (sexy, cute, beautiful, graceful)

Evolutionary standpoint of mate selection:

Attractiveness is the number one trait men choose to have in their life partners. From an evolutionary view, when choices are constrained, verifying the fertility is the highest priority underlying male mate choices. A woman's fertility is related to her observable physical features. Female fertility tends to peak in the mid 20s and decline at an increasing rate causing noticeable changes in appearance. The multi-billion dollar cosmetic industry reveals modern day women's underlying awareness of decreasing mate value [2].

Design standpoint of product selection:

In design, there is also a strong desire for attractive objects. Designers are constantly working to capture a beautiful form, a sexy look or a graceful construction. The aesthetics of a product is an essential ingredient in making a successful design. Donald Norman, in his book *Emotional Design*, states that aesthetics cannot be overlooked. Japanese researchers, Masaaki Kurosu and Kaori Kashimura, found through studies of two very different cultures, Japanese and Israeli, that attractive things are perceived as easier to use. In addition, Alice Isen, a psychologist, has shown that interacting with beautiful objects makes us happy, and happiness expands our thought process and facilitates creative thinking [3].

Case study: curves and proportions

Industrial design pioneer, Rowena Reed Kostellow, was a great influence on the study of proportions in product design. Her philosophy is based on a hierarchy of dominant, subdominant and subordinate elements within a design. Her studies emphasize how different elements, in relation to one another, can create harmonious balance. It is this balance that determines whether an object is pleasing to look at. In figure 1 we see these proportion studies executed successfully. The three elements have their own unique character, keeping in mind the importance of hierarchy in form and their placement creates a dynamic form that moves your eye and activates the surrounding space. Had the designer placed the large flat rectangle flush with the base, like the more voluminous form, these two forms would sacrifice some of their individual uniqueness, and the work would be less interesting to look at. Reed's studies were developed to train the designer's eye so s/he could apply these principles to product form development.

Figure 1. Rectilinear study

3.2 Social Status (lifestyle, social class, value system)

Evolutionary standpoint of mate selection:

Social status is the number one trait women look for in life partners. From an evolutionary standpoint, women had relatively less access to status, power and resources so they sought men with these traits to gain upward mobility. In addition, men who were higher in status had better access to resources for their offspring, so women are predicted to have evolved to value social status in long-term mates [4].

Design standpoint of product selection:

In today's product design world, social status reveals itself in the form of branding. In branding we see a clear parallel between the value and image of a product and the user's social class and lifestyle. Companies have realized that making a good product is not enough anymore. The product is only a part of the equation. What matters to a lot of people is what the product has to offer beyond its obvious function. This is why lifestyle branding has become an essential ingredient in delivering successful products. Lifestyle branding embodies the values, status and aspirations of certain groups and cultures. Brands try to convince their potential customers that the identity of their product will strengthen and enhance their lifestyle and values. By buying these products, individuals end up owning 'status symbols'. This allows them to associate publicly with a certain lifestyle.

Case study:

Method offers more than just cleaning supplies and they do so by tuning in to what their customers value. By understanding their users, Method created a brand that goes beyond the kitchen and bathroom. Method users are "people against dirty", who value non-toxic ingredients, an eco-conscious lifestyle, high-quality cleaning products, efficiency, and good design. All of this does not just happen during product use. Method analyzes the

whole product life cycle from pre-purchase to after life, creating a compelling story. They consider the whole experience from attracting the consumer with messaging and advertisement; engaging the consumer through fun and responsible product experience; and extending their relationship with their sustainable values.

3.3 Intelligence (smart, adaptive, intuitive, functions well)

Evolutionary standpoint of mate selection:

Studies show that intelligence is a necessity in trait selection. It can represent a broad measure of various capabilities including parenting, resource gathering, adaptability to change, and the ability to deal with competitors. Without some minimal level of intelligence, a person may have difficulties navigating the demands of social life and raising offspring [5].

Design standpoint of product selection:

Intelligence in design is measured according to how well a product functions. However, in today's design world, a product that just functions is not enough. What matters is how it functions. Is it intuitive to use and adaptable? Does it educate the user? Can she customize the way it works according to her needs? Similar to how a person's intelligence is measured, a product's intelligence is also measured according to its various capabilities. Users evaluate the product in terms of how well it adapts to their life, habits and needs.

Case study:

The Smart Gauge in figure 2, designed for Ford by Smart Design, opens a meaningful dialogue between the vehicle and its driver. Through feedback given from the car, the driver realizes how "well" she is driving. With simple and straight-forward feedback, the car enables the driver to develop a more petro-sensitive style of driving. This communication is done in a way that is easy to read while driving, visually stimulating, and intuitive. The capabilities that this interface offers allow the user to enhance their driving abilities and navigate the demands of a sustainable lifestyle [6].

Figure 2. Smart Gauge

3.4 Trustworthiness (loyal, safe, trusting)

Evolutionary standpoint of mate selection:

Studies show that trustworthiness is a necessary trait in mate selection. Trust requires that each partner is confident that the other partner will contribute positively to the relationship over a period of time. Trust is seen as the glue that holds relationships together. It has to be earned over time and through multiple shared experiences. Equally, a violation of trust is the primary reason behind relationship breakups. [7].

Design standpoint of product selection:

In design, trustworthiness is about how well a product lives up to its brand promise. Through advertising and messaging, brands work hard to attract a consumer base for their products. But attracting a consumer is not

enough. Brands need to *engage* their users during product use and *continue* their relationship by establishing a strong foundation based on shared values. What consumers ultimately want is to enjoy the benefits of the product the brand promised it would deliver. Brand loyalty does not happen over night, brands need to realize what their consumers value most and build a foundation where both party's values align.

Case Study:

Johnson & Johnson is seen as one of the most trusted brands in the world. For years, J&J worked hard to build a reputation of sincerity, honesty and concern for the public. In 1982 when seven people died after taking Tylenol that had been laced with cyanide, industry experts predicted that this event would be the end of the Tylenol brand, which accounted for 17% of the company's net income. However, within weeks, J&J withdrew 31 million bottles of Tylenol off the shelves and replaced them with tamper proof packaging, costing the company \$100 million. This immediate delivery reinforced their trusting nature amongst their consumers, and within months Tylenol exceeded its previous market share. J&J continues to hold the highest rank amongst brands that are perceived as trustworthy [8].

3.5 Empathy (understanding, adaptive, communicative)

Evolutionary standpoint of mate selection:

Many couples reported that the role of understanding plays an instrumental role in mate selection. Empathy comes in many forms, such as compassion, understanding and communication. Partners have said: "It's essential to always try and see the other person's point of view and seek balance." Psychologist Nina Fields found that the people who are most accurate in their perception of their spouses are able to respond empathetically towards them, and this results in more successful relationships [9].

Design standpoint of product selection:

Empathy in design is instrumental in understanding the needs of consumers. The foundation of empathetic design is observation. Through observation, researchers learn product and service requirements that users don't even know they want. Designers resort to an array of different methodologies to understand who their users are and how they can translate their needs into meaningful solutions. Whether it's role-playing, behavioral mapping or body-storming, it is important that we are empathetic throughout the design process.

Case Study:

Vicks realized an opportunity to grow in the thermometer market, and it is their empathetic design approach that allowed them to become the leading brand in the industry. When they set out to design a thermometer for young children, they realized that most digital thermometers mimicked the same shape as traditional mercury ones. Designers spent time observing how parents used current thermometers and how children interacted with them. Many parents were worried about misusing the thermometers, and children had a hard time keeping them in their mouths and under their arms. The design team successfully observed that parents did not know how deep to insert the thermometer into the baby's rectum. More often than not, parents inserted it too far, thinking that they would get a more accurate read. To solve this problem, a short probe was designed that helped guard against over-insertion. In addition, it's compact and ergonomic design made it easy to hold and control. The toddler underarm thermometer was designed so that it could be comfortably placed in the underarm while allowing for immediate temperature readings. The children's oral thermometer was designed with a flexible, curved probe that tucks easily under the child's tongue, making it easier for the child to hold in their mouth [10].

3.6 Ambitious (innovative, forward thinking, aspiring, motivated)

Evolutionary standpoint of mate selection:

Couples reported that ambition is a trait that keeps relationships on their feet. While individual ambition brings personal achievement, the results of the achievement are shared between couples. Their individual excitement, energy and success infiltrates positively into the relationship, allowing for a shared experience [11].

Design standpoint of product selection:

In the design world, ambition reveals itself in the form of innovation. As competition in the market grows, so does the demand for innovative design solutions. Innovative thinking brings a fresh take on what we know and allows for new experiences.

Case Study:

The Nike Plus revolutionized running. Nike and Apple capitalized on the insights into human motivation by using goals, challenges, support and competition, all presented in a user-friendly interface. With their innovative solutions, users have reported that they have become more ambitious with their runs. With this system, runners track their progress, become friends with other runners around the world, and customize their goals. All of which enables motivation and encouragement while sharing success with peers through the Nike network.

3.7 Exciting (good sense of humor, positively surprising, creative)

Evolutionary standpoint of mate selection:

Psychologist John Gottman hypothesizes that happy couples typically use five times more positive than negative behaviors during arguments. One such tactic is using humor to break the tension. Also, bringing romance and unexpected positive behaviors strengthens the bond and reassures mates that they are still special [12].

Design standpoint of product selection:

Bringing excitement to design benefits the relationship between user product interactions. Geke Ludden and Paul Hekkert explain that a positive surprise reaction to a product can be beneficial to both the user and the designer. The designer benefits from a surprise reaction because it can draw attention to the product, leading to increased word of mouth. The user benefits from the surprise because the design becomes more interesting to interact with, leaving a memorable experience for the user [13].

Case Study:

Honey Pop Chair by Tokujin Yoshioka is made out of 120 sheets of glassine paper, which are piled together to a thickness of 1 cm. Cut into appropriate shapes, it is received flat and opens outwards like an accordion. Eventually the chair finds its form by deriving its shape from its sitter. Paper is not perceived as a strong material, as a result, this design has people question its structural elements and wonder how it holds such heavy weight. Awakened curiosity, surprise and excitement in the user.

4. Design Toolkit

Defining and analyzing the ideal traits from a mate and product standpoint is only the first step in this study. To facilitate the application of these insights, I developed a series of design strategies that link to each desired trait. Created in the form of inspiration cards, designers can call upon any of the strategies when they wish to imbue their work with any of these traits. The toolkit is designed so that each trait has its own deck. The toolkit is divided into 7 categories (figure 3). These categories are the traits I illustrated above: Attractiveness, Social

Status, Intelligence, Trustworthiness, Empathy, Ambitious, and Exciting. There are a total of 8 decks. Knowing that creativity is boundless I wanted designers to keep adding to the card set as they came up with their own strategies. Therefore, I have added blank cards to the set as well.

Figure 3. 7 Trait Framework

Each category is broken down into strategy groups. Within each strategy group, there are 8 – 13 strategy cards. These strategy cards explain how the designer can incorporate a trait into their design. Figure 4 illustrates the architecture of the toolkit.

Figure 4. Architecture of the toolkit

4.1 Main Category and Strategy Groups

Figure 5 illustrates the first component of the toolkit. The front of this card has the trait written. The back of the card explains how that trait relates to mate selection from an evolutionary standpoint and to product selection from a design standpoint.

Figure 5. First component of the toolkit: trait card

Figure 6 illustrates the second component of the toolkit. The front of the card has synonyms of that trait. These are the words that were frequently used during my product design interviews. For instance, when we talked about an exciting product or mate, the words “lively, fun, interesting, different and unexpected” came up numerous times. The back of this card, illustrates the strategy groups. Each trait is broken down into strategy groups. For instance, exciting is broken down into ‘use of surprise’, ‘sense of humor’ and ‘exceeding expectations’. These denominations are based on existing design approaches that have achieved a high level of excitement. The last blank line, line d, reminds the designer that they too can add a strategy group.

Figure 6. Second component of toolkit: strategy groups

4.2 Strategy Cards

Figure 7 illustrates the third component to the toolkit, the strategy card. For instance, the strategy group, “Use of Surprise,” has 12 strategy cards. Below is an example of one of them. On the front you can read what the strategy is. On the back of the card, there is an example of how this strategy has been used by a designer.

Figure 7. Third component of toolkit: strategy cards

4.3 Testing the Cards:

To test the cards, I received feedback from 2 design firms in New York City; Smart Design (figure 8) and Jailbreak Collective. The comments from Smart Design were that the words from the trait cards, as much as the strategies themselves can help the design process. It can establish an easier foundation to talk to clients about the merits of ‘emotional design’. It can also make it easier to explain how and why consumers look for the same traits in people as they do in their products. The framework was also referred to as a great “check list” for developing concepts. A designer from Jailbreak Collective said: “It verbalizes and codifies all the different tricks we use to come up with our products. And after years of doing this, I have to tip my hat to you... I never had such a clear, well-stated understanding of what worked.”

Figure 8. Illustration of use

Dan Formosa, co-founder of Smart Design was also very interested in this concept and proposed that we develop a workshop based on my research. As a result, we came up with a workshop, which was carried out at Arizona States University’s Exposed Conference. For the workshop a group of 35 people were broken into 7 different groups. They were told to think of traits they would want in a product that would make them happy and traits that would make them miserable. 4 of the 7 groups were then sent to the adjacent room to work. When those groups left, the topic for the 3 remaining groups were changed. These groups were told to switch the word “product” with “mate”. These groups were asked to think of attributes of a mate that would make them happy and miserable. After 40 minutes of brainstorming the groups came back and shared their responses. The traits that were used to explain the product and the mate were almost identical. The most commonly used words to explain what made them happy were attractive / sexy, trustworthy, intelligent / smart, empathetic and exciting /surprising.

5. Conclusion

This research has illustrated the importance and value of understanding the essential traits desired in long-term mates as they relate to product design. It has also provided the facilitation to apply these traits to design. When designers anthropomorphize their products, they tap into something deep within all of us. We are complex creatures, but there is a lot of similarity in our deepest desires. It is these traits, selected over time, that should be anthropomorphized by designers. This is where my research started and it has evolved from meaningful insights to actionable strategies. If our goal as designers is to create an emotional connection between users and objects, then imbuing our designs with these top traits makes a lot of sense. This design toolkit is not definitive. It exists to help researchers and designers produce successful designs that create an emotional connection with consumers. The toolkit is intentionally designed to grow, allowing continuous input from designers themselves. The next step for this research is to build a digital version of the cards. This will allow the design community to more easily share insights and strategies within the 7-trait framework that has been established.

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